

First report of myrmecophagy by *Euryopsis* sp. (Araneae: Theridiidae) on *Tetraponera rufonigra* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from India

ASHIRWAD TRIPATHY^{1*}, ARUN PRATAP SINGH¹ & HIMENDER BHARTI²

¹Forest Entomology Discipline, Forest Protection Division, Forest Research Institute, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, 248006, India
 Email: ranoteaps@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0981-9050>

²Department of Zoology & Environmental Sciences, Punjabi University, Patiala, Punjab, 147002, India
 Email: himenderbharti@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5996-1808>

*Corresponding author email: ashirwadresearch101@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7772-2616>

Abstract

We report the predation of *Tetraponera rufonigra* (Formicidae) by *Euryopsis* sp. (Theridiidae) for the first time. This is a first ever report of any predator documentation on *T. rufonigra*. Additionally, an updated checklist of myrmecophagy by *Euryopsis* sp. has been presented. This documentation has been done at New Forest Campus, Forest Research Institute, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India.

Key words: *Euryopsis*, *Tetraponera rufonigra*, myrmecophagy, Theridiidae

Tetraponera rufonigra Jerdon (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) has emerged as a significant medical pest in urban areas of India and Southeast Asia, notorious for its painful sting that can lead to severe anaphylactic reactions (Ratnatilaka & Dias, 2011; Fernando et al., 2015). The venom, which contains acids and alkaloids, triggers toxic reactions, including both local and systemic responses like anaphylaxis (Potiwat & Sitcharungsi, 2015). Although this species mimicked by many other species such as *Myrmarachne melanocephala* (Salticidae) (Sarma et al., 2024), *Aetius decollatus* (Coriniidae) (Sudhin et al., 2017), *Ampulex dementer* (Ampulicidae) (Ohl et al., 2014), and some other *Ampulex* sp. (Anagha & Girish, 2019). But there have been no reports on the predation of *T. rufonigra*.

Predator-prey interactions are a cornerstone of ecological research, shedding light on the complex dynamics that govern ecosystems (Abrams, 2000; Orrick et al., 2024). Spiders, as one of the most diverse groups of terrestrial predators, play a significant role in regulating insect populations (Nyffeler & Benz, 1987). Despite the danger ants pose to with strong mandibles, the ability to spray formic acid, and strength in numbers, only about 0.3% of known spider species feed on them (Cushing, 2012). Myrmecophagy is rare among most other taxa for these reasons (Eisner et al., 1993).

However, the spider family Theridiidae likely diversified alongside ants during the Cretaceous period (Liu et al., 2016), leading to a relatively high number of myrmecophagous species and specialized hunting strategies, as seen in the genus *Euryopsis* (Carico, 1978; Líznavá & Pekár, 2019). Among these arachnid predators, the genus *Euryopsis* (family Theridiidae) stands out due to its specialized predation on ants (Aceves-Aparicio et al., 2022). Members of this genus are reported to be myrmecophagous, based on a relatively small number of observations of predation (Pekár & Cárdenas, 2015; Porter & Eastmond, 1982). Various spider families exhibit myrmecophagy, including Araneidae, Corinnidae, Deinopidae, Eresidae, Gnaphosidae, Linyphiidae, Myrmecicultoridae, Oecobiidae, Oonopidae, Oxyopidae, Pholcidae, Salticidae, Scytodidae, Theridiidae, Thomisidae, and Zodariidae (Cushing, 1997; Cushing, 2012; Cushing et al., 2022).

The genus *Euryopsis* encompasses 82 species distributed across different habitats worldwide. In India, only two species are present: *Euryopsis episinoides* Walckenaer, 1847 and *Euryopsis nubila* Simon, 1889 (WSC, 2024; Caleb & Sankaran, 2024). However, observations on their hunting behaviour in the Indian context are scanty.

Myrmecophagous spiders use specialized hunting strategies to capture ants (Jackson & Nelson, 2012). These tactics include building webs directly above ant nest entrances (MacKay, 1982), attacking ants from behind, and retreating from the nest area between and after attacks (Pekár, 2004). In facultatively myrmecophagous spiders, these behaviours are observed only when hunting ants and no other prey (Cushing, 2012). Some specialist spider myrmecophages may also consume specific parts of the ant to optimize nutrient intake (Pekár et al., 2010). For example, spiders raised and reared in laboratory conditions *Euryopsis episinoides* showed higher survival and reproductive rates when fed solely on ants compared to a diet of *Drosophila* Fallén, 1823. This suggests they efficiently metabolize ants and have difficulty meeting nutritional needs with other diets (Líznarová & Pekár, 2016).

Field and laboratory observations by Líznarová and Pekár (2019) revealed the trophic niche and capture efficacy of *Euryopsis episinoides*, confirming it as an ant-eating specialist with effective capture strategies. Despite this specialization, *E. episinoides* can also capture alternative prey. Prey acceptance experiments showed that *E. episinoides* accepts various prey types, but ants, termites, and fruit flies were preferred (Líznarová & Pekár, 2019). Additionally, spiders that specialize in eating certain types of ants may produce venom more effective against their preferred ant species, such as formicine ants over myrmicine ants (Pekár, 2009).

Ants, although the most abundant arthropods in many terrestrial habitats (Holldobler & Wilson, 1990), are unsuitable prey for most spider species due to their danger (strong mandibles, stings) and unpalatability (defensive chemicals). Consequently, most euryphagous spiders avoid ants as prey (Edwards & Jackson, 1994; Líznarová & Pekár, 2013). However, *Euryopsis* spiders capture ants efficiently by casting silk over their prey from a distance, preventing counter-attacks (Carico, 1978; Aceves-Aparicio et al., 2022).

The hunting process in *Euryopsis sp.* typically begins with the spider casting silk onto the prey while circling around it. After biting the prey, the spider wraps it in more silk and waits for the venom to paralyze it. Once the prey is immobilized, the spider attaches the prey to its spinnerets and carries it away to consume (Líznarová & Pekár, 2019).

During a field survey of ants at Forest Research Institute, Dehradun, Uttarakhand (30.344400, 78.002900) on 29 May, 2023 at 1:40 pm it was observed that one *Euryopsis sp.* (female) (Fig. 2) was hanging straight down from a leaning *Toona ciliata* tree by holding three individuals of *Tetraponera rufonigra* ants simultaneously in its grasp (Fig. 1). The ant was double the size of the spider. The hanging silk was around 1 m long and the spider was swinging along with the ants. During the hanging state it was observed that the silk used for hanging was transparent in nature (dry silk) and the silk used for holding the *T. rufonigra* was white in colour (viscid silk) and with legs the spider was coiling the silk and making a white ball out of it during this swinging state. This swinging or dangling stage is the third phase of the feeding sequence as mentioned by Aceves-Aparicio et al., (2022) in *Euryopsis umblicata*.

Though in the Moist Shiwalik Sal forest of Dehradun all the possible mimic organisms of *T. rufonigra* are found i.e., *Myrmarachne melanocephala* (Salticidae), *Aetius decollatus* (Coriniidae), and *Ampulex sp.* (Ampulicidae) along with *Euryopsis sp.* which is not a myrmecomorph of *T. rufonigra*. However, *Euryopsis sp.* was observed preying on other ant species found in the Moist Shiwalik Sal forest area. However, only this single predation record was observed at New Forest Campus of Forest Research Institute, Dehradun during the course of 2.5 years field survey. The Forest Research Institute, Dehradun come across the Moist Shiwalik Sal forest (Champion & Sheth, 1968) which is a Sal (*Shorea robusta*: Dipterocarpaceae) dominated forest. The new forest campus of F.R.I., Dehradun was planted with many indigenous and exotic plant species which creates a different kind of habitat as compare to the nearby forest area. However, the fauna diversity and the locality factor/ site factors are more or less same as compare to the nearby *Shorea robusta* dominated forest.

Toona ciliata M. Roem. (Meliaceae) also known as Indian Mahogany is a large deciduous tree with a spreading crown, commonly attaining a height of 20-30 m and a girth of 1.8-3 m. Bark dark grey or reddish-brown, smooth up to middle age, afterwards rough, with shallow reticulate cracks exfoliating in irregular woody scales. These exfoliating and scaly bark acts as a shelter for Theridiidae spiders on the tree. Though this spider does not make nest but take shelter underneath the bark.

FIGURE 1- a) silk ball (yellow arrow), Three *Tetraponera rufonigra* prey (black arrow); a) to e) Ventral side of *Euryopsis* sp. (♀) with the silk ball formation, f) Dorsal side of *Euryopsis* sp. (♀)

FIGURE 2: Dorsal (left) and Ventral (right) surface of the *Euryopsis* sp. (♀)

This behaviour aligns with the three-phase predation sequence described for *Euryopsis umblicata* (Aceves-Aparicio et al., 2022). In first phase it employs its hind legs to pull viscid silk from its spinnerets and attach it to the ant during tumbles, preventing the ant from escaping. The spider then drops off the tree trunk, secured by the silk line connected to both the ant and the trunk. In the next phase, the spider circles the ant, entangling it in more viscid silk before biting it. The spider might switch to dry silk during this stage, as suggested by Carico (1978) for *Euryopsis funebris*. Finally, the spider releases the ant from the trunk and carries it away, often while it dangles from a strand of silk, to feed on it.

Previous studies have noted a consistent hunting pattern in these spiders (Hale et al., 2018). They do not make web or nest instead a string of silk is used to hunt the prey (Hale et al., 2018; Líznavá & Pekár, 2019). Some reported it as a prey specific in the field (Hale et al., 2018) while some reported it as stenophagous with a very narrow prey range (Pekár & Cárdenas 2015). In laboratory many ants were used as experimental prey to study the preference in different *Euryopsis* sp. (Pekár & Cárdenas 2015; Líznavá & Pekár, 2019) but still the literature is scanty on it. The well studied species is *Euryopsis episinoides* as it is widely distributed across the world (WSC, 2024; Pekár & Cárdenas 2015; Líznavá & Pekár, 2016; Hale et al., 2018; Líznavá & Pekár, 2019). Another study by Pekár & Cárdenas (2015) found that the innate preference of prey of the spiderlings of *E. episinoides* can be altered and be made familiar to prey which are less beneficial.

Huseynov et al., (2008) proposed five categories of spider myrmecophages: (1) non-acceptors of ants (the majority of spider species); (2) reluctant acceptors that do prey on ants but prefer other prey; (3) indifferent acceptors that feed indiscriminately on ants and other prey; (4) facultative ant choosers that prefer ants to other prey; (5) obligatory ant choosers that feed exclusively on ants (unless severely food deprived).

Our observation contributes to the understanding of ant-spider interactions, revealing that *Euryopsis* sp. can effectively prey on *Tetraoponera rufonigra*. In addition to this observation, we have also compiled the myrmecophagy reports by *Euryopsis* spp. around the world (Table 1). Given the rarity of myrmecophagy, further studies are needed to explore the full ecological implications of these interactions in the forests of India.

Table 1: Updated checklist of myrmecophagy by *Euryopsis* spp. (Adopted from Cushing, 2012)

Spider Myrmecophage	Global Distribution	Category of Myrmecophage	Ant Prey	Notes on Biology	References
<i>Euryopsis californica</i>	USA, Mexico	I/F	<i>Pogonomyrmex rugosus</i>	Reported feeding on <i>Pogonomyrmex rugosus</i> Emery.	MacKay, 1982
		I/F	<i>Veromessor pergandei</i>	-	Hale et al., 2018
<i>Euryopsis coki</i>	USA	I/F	<i>Pogonomyrmex salinus</i>	Preys on <i>Pogonomyrmex salinus</i> Olsen (publ. as <i>P. owyheeii</i>). Spider captures ant on the mound by trapping ant against ground with sticky silk. Bites on leg. Ant swings offground on thread. When paralyzed, spider drags it away using a web sling attached to the ant and to the spinnerets.	Porter & Eastmond, 1982
<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (publ. as <i>E. acuminata</i>)	Cape Verde, Mediterranean to Turkey, Georgia, Israel. Introduced to	I/F	<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	Feeds on ants. Attacks <i>Crematogaster</i> ants and transports each attached to spinnerets.	Berland, 1933

	South Africa, Reunion, India, China				
<i>Euryopis formosa</i>	USA, Canada	I/F	<i>Pogonomyrmex salinus</i>	Captures and carries workers of <i>Pogonomyrmex salinus</i> Olsen. Carries ant across ground. One attack described: spider bit gaster, released ant, moved to front and waited, reapproached paralyzed ant, climbed onto ant and began dragging across ant nest using web sling.	Clark & Blom, 1992
<i>Euryopis funebris</i>	Canada, USA. Introduced to South Africa	F/O	-	Throws adhesive silk over ant passing by on tree trunk and fastens it to tree. Encircles ant, throwing silk. Bites leg. Cuts paralyzed ant free and carries it to crack or crevice or drops on line to feed.	Archer, 1946; Carico, 1978
<i>Euryopis scriptipes</i>	USA, Mexico	I/F	-	Feeds on ants.	Levi, 1954
<i>Euryopis texana</i>	USA, Mexico	I/F	-	Female reported preying upon moving lines of small ants	Gertsch, 1979
<i>Euryopis umbilicata</i>	Australia (Queensland)	O	<i>Camponotus consobrinus</i>	<i>Euryopis umbilicata</i> hide under the bark of <i>Eucalyptus</i> trees during the day and emerge at evening twilight. They actively found to hunt the <i>Camponotus consobrinus</i> that also forage on <i>Eucalyptus</i> tree.	Aceves-Aparicio et al., 2022
Other <i>Euryopis</i> spp.		I/F	-	Prey on ants. Throw adhesive silk over ants and fasten to trees.	Carico, 1978; Levi, 1954; Gertsch, 1979
<i>Euryopis</i> sp.	India	O	<i>Tetraoponera rufonigra</i>	Three individuals of <i>Tetraoponera rufonigra</i> ants simultaneously grasped. The observation was taken during the swinging or dangling stage which is the third phase of the feeding sequence.	Present Study

In Table 1, the various spider myrmecophages that have been documented from the literature are categorized as (R) Reluctant acceptors, (I) Indifferent acceptors, (F) Facultative ant choosers, or (O) Obligatory ant choosers based upon information about their biology provided in the literature (Cushing, 2012).

Acknowledgements

The authors express their gratitude to Dr. Praveen Kumar Verma, Scientist D, Forest Botany Division, F.R.I., Dehradun, for his assistance in identifying the tree species. We extend our thanks to Mr. Rishikesh Tripathi, Ph.D. Scholar, for confirming the spider genus, and to Mr. Pankaj Pratap Singh, Ph.D. Scholar, F.R.I., for his invaluable field assistance. Thanks to Miss Sifan Priyadarshini, Ph.D. Scholar, MSCBDU for checking the manuscript. Special thanks are also due to Miss Devi Priyadarshini, Scientist D, RMNH, Bhubaneswar, for reviewing the manuscript draft.

References

- Abrams, P.A. 2000. The evolution of predator-prey interactions: Theory and Evidence. *Annual review of ecology, evolution, and systematics*, 31, 79-105.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.31.1.79>
- Aceves-Aparicio, A., Narendra, A., McLean, D.J., Lowe, E.C., Christian, M., Wolff, J.O., Schneider, J.M., and Herberstein, M.E. 2022. Fast acrobatic maneuvers enable arboreal spiders to hunt dangerous prey. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 119, e2205942119
- Anagha, S. and Girish K.P. 2019. A taxonomic study of the genus *Ampulex* Jurine (Hymenoptera: Ampulicidae) from India with the description of one species from Kerala. *Devagiri Journal of Science*, 5(1): 1-16.
- Archer, A.F. 1946. The Theridiidae or comb-footed spiders of Alabama. *Museum Papers of the Alabama Museum of Natural History*, vol. 22, 5–67 pp.
- Berland, L. 1933. Contribution a l'etudedelabiologieedes arachnides," *Archives de Zoologie Exp'perimentale et G'en'erale*, 76(1), 1–23.
- Caleb, J.T.D. and Sankaran, P.M. 2024. Araneae of India. Version 2024, online at <http://www.indianspiders.in> [11 July, 2024]
- Carico, J.E. 1978. Predatory behaviour of *Euryopsis funeris* (Hentz) (Araneae: Theridiidae) and the evolutionary significance of web reduction, *Symposium of the Zoological Society of London*, 42, 51–58.
- Champion, H.G. and Seth, S.K. 1968. A Revised Survey of the Forest Types of India. Government of India Press, Howrah, pp 404.
- Clark, W.H., & Blom, P.E. 1992. Notes on spider (Theridiidae, Salticidae) predation of the harvester ant, *Pogonomyrmex salinus* Olsen (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Myrmicinae), and a possible parasitoid fly (Chloropidae), *Great Basin Naturalist*, 52, 385–386.
- Cushing, P.E. 1997. Myrmecomorphy and Myrmecophily in Spiders: A Review. *The Florida Entomologist*, 80 (2): 165-193.
- Cushing, P.E. 2012. Spider-ant associations: An updated review of myrmecomorphy, myrmecophily, and myrmecophagy in spiders. In *Psyche* (London). Hindawi Limited.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/151989>
- Cushing, P.E., Brückner, A., Rogers, J.W., & Horner, N.V. 2022. Trophic specialization of a newly described spider ant symbiont, *Myrmecicultor chihuahuensis* (Araneae: Myrmecicultoridae). *The Journal of Arachnology*, 50(2), 250–255.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/27233966>
- Eisner, T., Baldwin, I. T., Conner, J., 1993. Circumvention of prey defense by a predator: Ant lion vs. ant. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.*, 90, 6716–6720.
- Fernando, K. S. S. D., Dias, R. K. S., & Rajapaksha, R. P. K. C. 2015. Functional morphology of the sting apparatus of *Tetraponera rufonigra* (Smith, F.) (Formicidae, Pseudomyrmecinae). In 10th ANeT International Conference. University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka.
- Gertsch, W.J. 1979. *American Spiders*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York, NY, USA, 2nd edition.
- Hale, A., Bougie, T., Henderson, E., Sankovitz, M., West, M., and Purcell, J. 2018. Notes on hunting behaviour of the spider *Euryopsis californica* Banks, 1904 (Araneae: Theridiidae), a novel predator of *Veromessor pergandei* (Mayr, 1886) harvester ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae), *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist*, 94(3), 141-145.
<https://doi.org/10.3956/2018-94.3.141>
- Huseynov, E. F., Jackson, R. R. & Cross, F. R., 2008. The meaning of predatory specialization as illustrated by *Aelurillus m-nigrum*, an ant-eating jumping spider (Araneae: Salticidae) from Azerbaijan, *Behavioural Processes*, 77(3), 389–399.

- Jackson, R. R. & Nelson, X. J. 2012. Specialized predation of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) by spiders (Araneae). *Myrmecological News*, 17, 33–49.
- Levi, H.W. 1954. Spiders of the genus *Euryopis* from North and Central America, *American Museum Novitates*, 1666, 1–48.
- Liu, J., May-Collado, L. J., Pekár, S., Agnarsson, I., 2016. A revised and dated phylogeny of cobweb spiders (Araneae, Araneoidea, Theridiidae): A predatory Cretaceous lineage diversifying in the era of the ants (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* 94, 658–675.
- Líznarová, E. & S. Pekár. 2016. Metabolic specialisation on preferred prey and constraints in the utilisation of alternative prey in an ant-eating spider. *Zoology*, 119, 464–470.
- Líznarová, E., and Pekár, S., 2019. Trophic niche and capture efficacy of an ant-eating spider, *Euryopis episinoides* (Araneae: Theridiidae), *The Journal of Arachnology*, 47(1), 45-51.
<https://doi.org/10.1636/0161-8202-47.1.45>
- MacKay, W.P. 1982. The effect of predation of western widow spiders (Araneae: Theridiidae) on harvester ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae), *Oecologia* 53, 406–411.
<https://doi.org/10.13102/sociobiology.v66i4.4431>
- Nyffeler, M., and Benz, G. 1987. Spiders in natural pest control: A review. *Journal of Applied Entomology*, 103(1-5), 321-339.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0418.1987.tb00992.x>
- Ohl, M., Lohrmann, V., Breitzkreuz, L., Kirsche, L., Krause, S. 2014. The Soul-Sucking Wasp by Popular Acclaim – Museum Visitor Participation in Biodiversity Discovery and Taxonomy. *PLoS ONE*, 9(4), e95068.
doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0095068
- Orrick, K., Sommer, N., Rowland, F., Ferraro, K. 2024. Predator-prey interactions across hunting mode, spatial domain size, and habitat complexities. *Ecology*.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.4316>
- Pekár, S. & M. Cárdenas. 2015. Innate prey preference overridden by familiarisation with detrimental prey in a specialised myrmecophagous predator. *The Science of Nature*, 102, 8.
- Pekár, S. 2004. Predatory behaviour of two European ant-eating spiders (Araneae, Zodariidae). *Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society*, 32, 31–41.
- Pekár, S., Mayntz, D., Ribeiro, T., & Herberstein, E. 2010. Specialist ant-eating spiders selectively feed on different body parts to balance nutrient intake. *Animal Behaviour*, 79, 1301–1306.
- Porter, S.D. & D. A. Eastmond. 1982. *Euryopis coki* (Theridiidae), a spider that preys on *Pogonomyrmex* ants. *The Journal of Arachnology*, 10, 275–277.
- Potiwat, R., Sitcharungsi, R., 2015. Ant allergens and hypersensitivity reactions in response to ant stings. *Asian Pacific J. Allergy Immunol*, 33, 267–275.
- Ratnatilaka, G., Dias, R.K.S., 2011. Severe anaphylaxis following ant bites. *Ceylon Med. J.*, 56, 34–35.
- Sarma, D., Das, J. & Khanikor, B. 2024. New records of ant-mimicking spiders from North-East India. *Int J Trop Insect Sci.*, 44, 983–988.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42690-024-01200-0>
- Sudhin, P., Nafin, K.S., Simmons, Z., and Sudhikumar, A.V. (2017). On the type species of the genus *Aetius* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1896: The first description of male with notes on cymbial notch and mating plug (Araneae: Corinnidae: Castianeirinae). *Zootaxa*, 4154 (4), 489-500.
- WSC (2024) <https://wsc.nmbe.ch/genus/3482> (accessed on 10/07/24)